

Covariance Matrix for Portfolio Selection on Vietnam Stock Market

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Thu Trang Dang ⁽²⁾Thi Thu Ha Pham ⁽³⁾Thi Thu Huong Do

⁽¹⁾ ⁽²⁾ ⁽³⁾University of Economics - Technology for Industries, Vietnam

Correspondence: Thu Trang Dang, 456 Minh Khai, Hai Ba Trung, Ha Noi

Abstract:

The objective of this dissertation is to investigate that whether the investors can improve the performance of minimum – variance optimized portfolios by altering the estimators of covariance matrix input. Besides, based on the results of out – of – sample portfolio performance metrics, the dissertation is going to select the suitable estimators of covariance matrix for portfolio optimization on Vietnam stock market.

Keywords: Covariance matrix, Vietnam stock market

1. Introduction

The Vietnamese stock market has been developing for 20 years since the Ho Chi Minh City Stock Exchange officially came into operation in July 2000 with the first two tickers, REE and SAM, hitting the historic turning point of the Vietnam stock market. So far, the Vietnam stock market has had flourish development. The number of listed and registered companies trading on two stock exchanges is 1.605 companies, with the stock volume of 150 billion. The market capitalization as of the beginning of 2020 reached nearly 5.7 million billion VND, accounting for 102.74% of GDP, thereby, showing the significant role of Vietnam stock market to the economy.

Vietnam's stock market operates with three official exchanges, including two listed (HOSE, HNX) and one unlisted (UPCoM) stock exchange. In specifically, Ho Chi Minh City Stock Exchange (HOSE) is considered the largest scale exchange. By the end of 2019, HOSE had 382 listed companies; the trading volume reached 8.8 billion shares, the average trading value reached more than 4,000 billion VND/session. Market capitalization on HOSE accounts for 88% of the total market, equivalent to 54.3% of GDP. Enterprises to be listed on the HOSE have to achieve higher standards in terms of charter capital, time of operation, performance, information disclosure, and shareholders structure. Specifically, enterprises registered to list on the HOSE need to have the minimum charter capital contributed at the time of listing registration based on the book value of VND 120 billion, higher than the amount of VND 30 billion on the Ha Noi Stock Exchange (HNX). Regarding the time of operation, enterprises must have at least two years of operation as a joint-stock company before the time of registration for listing on HOSE while on HNX it takes one year. Regarding performance criteria, HOSE stipulates that listed enterprises must have profitable business activities in the previous two years, one year more than required by HNX. Regarding shareholder structure, HOSE requires businesses to have a minimum of 300 non-major shareholders holding at least 20% of the voting stock of the company. For HNX, this standard is a minimum of 100 shareholders holding at least 15% of the shares. Especially, HOSE has higher listing standards for information disclosure. Accordingly, the company must disclose all its debts to internal persons, major shareholders, and related persons.

The development of Vietnam's stock market has attracted a growing number of domestic and foreign investors, from 3000 trading accounts in 2000 to 2.5 million accounts in the current period. In particularly, there are about 33,000 accounts of foreign organizations and individuals with a total value of securities held nearly 35 billion USD as of June 30, 2020.

2. Literature review

Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT) has been playing an important role in the selection and construction of investment portfolios for over 65 years, since it was firstly introduced by Harry Markowitz in his "Portfolio Selection" (1952) article. The framework of MPT is to attain as highest return as possible for a certain level of risk through structuring the optimal weights of various assets (Iyiola, 2012). Although it is broadly employed in

practical investment activities, the main assumptions of MPT model have been facing great challenges in recent years. One of the main reasons comes from the two main inputs of MPT that are the mean and the covariance matrix of asset returns.

To implement the technique in practice, investors have to estimate the mean and the covariance matrix of assets' return. At this point, sample mean as well as covariance matrix approaches are usually employed. However, these estimators are not really stable in many cases because of estimation error, this makes the weights of portfolio fluctuate continuously over time. As a result, the mean – variance portfolios are difficult to be applied in practice by the portfolio managers. Moreover, many well – known empirical evidences showed that these portfolios underperformed in term of mean and variance metrics during the out-of-sample period (Michaud, 1989).

In general, there are two ways to overcome the challenges of MPT that are to initiate the new approaches for estimating the expected return and covariance matrix of assets in portfolio optimization. The well-known models have been utilized to estimate expected return parameter such as Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) and Fama – French models. The CAPM, which is considered as one – factor model, describes a linkage between systematic risk and expected return of assets. Meanwhile, Fama – French states that the expected returns of assets should be explained by some other variables besides of beta coefficient of CAPM such as size risk, value risk factor, profitability, and investment factor. In addition, the robust estimators are also applied by the researchers and portfolio managers to improve the expected return estimation, for example the truncated/trimmed mean or winsorized mean are employed by Martin, Clark and Green in 2010. Moreover, the other robust estimation methods like M – estimator or S – estimator, Bayes – Stein estimator are developed to solve the non-stationary returns limitation in estimating the expected return input.

The improvement of estimating assets' expected returns is one of the ways to remedy MPT's shortcomings. However, the results of Merton's research (1980) showed that it is not easy to measure the expected return (μ). In most asset price models, they made an assumption that there is a linkage between the assets' expected return and the market's expected return (r), in which (r) is constant overtime. Although this assumption makes the assets' expected return estimation to be easier, it would still take a very long time series to estimate μ accurately (Merton, 1980). Moreover, all we know that the assumption of constant expected return is not reasonable, but if this assumption is relaxed, the estimating μ will be even harder. This paves the way for a second research direction, selecting portfolios based on the covariance matrix estimation instead of the expected return estimation. The estimation of covariance matrix parameter is an important research direction that researchers have paid special attention in the recent period, due to the potential of this method in improving stability and minimizing risk in selecting the investment portfolios.

The instability of the mean-variance portfolios comes from estimating the mean assets return. Thus, the minimum – variance portfolios have recently been used by many researchers and portfolio managers. In this method, the investigated portfolios are primarily based on the estimation of covariance matrix, making them less sensitive to the estimation errors (Jagannathan and Ma, 2003). Moreover, Jagannathan and Ma suggested that “the estimation error in the sample mean is so large that nothing is lost in ignoring the mean altogether”. This argument also provides detailed empirical evidence showing that the minimum-variance portfolio is likely to outperforms on Sharpe's ratio and other performance metrics in out-of-sample period than any other mean-variance portfolios (DeMiguel, 2005; Jagannathan and Ma, 2003).

Demiguel (2009) stated that although the minimum-variance portfolio does not depend on the mean returns estimation, it is still under great impact of estimation error. The sensitivity of the minimum-variance portfolio to estimation error is quite interesting. “These portfolios are based on the sample covariance matrix, which is the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) for normally distributed returns. Moreover, MLEs are theoretically the most efficient for the assumed distribution; that is, these estimators have the smallest asymptotic variance provided the data follows the assumed distribution”. At this point, a question was raised that why the sample covariance matrix generates unsuitable portfolios. Huber (2004) answered that “the efficiency of MLEs based

on assuming normality of returns is highly sensitive to deviations of the asset-return distribution from the assumed (normal) distribution. In particular, MLEs based on the normality assumption are not necessarily the most efficient for data that depart even slightly from normality". For portfolio selection, this is very useful as comprehensive evidence indicates that the empirical return distribution is generally different from normal distribution.

Moreover, although the core of minimum - variance portfolio researches relies solely on how to estimate reliably the covariance matrix, however, almost traditional approaches of covariance matrix estimation such as using the sample covariance matrix (SCM) or ordinary least squares (OLS) face many problems in the case of high-dimensional portfolios. Having large dimensionality means that it is easier to get unexpected and uncontrollable errors in some of computational steps, and the sample data may not be enough for the estimation of the true covariance matrix. These lead to the estimated covariance matrix to become ill-conditioned or even singular which is very popular in matrix computation research. Consequently, the portfolios selected from considering the sample covariance matrix often perform poorly and fail in generating profit. To solve this problem, some new estimators of covariance matrix are conducted by many researchers and portfolio managers. There have been many approaches proposed in the literature, and among them, Ledoit and Wolf (2003) proposed to select the optimal portfolios by using the shrinkage estimator of covariance matrix. This method is a combination between a rough sample covariance matrix and a high-structured target matrix to achieve the balance between bias and variance. The balance can be customized, which is the trade-off between bias and estimation errors recognized by shrinkage coefficients. The shrinkage technique shows theoretically and empirically attractive approach to a high-dimensional portfolio's covariance estimation problem since it ensures a well-defined covariance matrix is achieved. Liu (2014) estimated the covariance matrix by applying the weighted average of different shrinkage target matrices, instead of using a single shrinkage target matrix as Ledoit and Wolf method. Next, by inheriting the potentials and development of Random Matrix Theory, Ledoit and Wolf extended their pilot works (Ledoit & Wolf, 2017a, 2017b) by using a nonlinear transformation applied for the eigenvalues considering solely the sample data. Also, coefficient asymptotically leads to the maximization of the out-of-sample expected utility. Then, they performed both numerical and empirical investigation where the out-of-sample behavior of the obtained estimator is analyzed and it shows remarkable improvements over the simple diversification, and its robustness is expressed to the deviations from normality. As a matter of fact, DeMiguel et al. (2013) provided an important review paper of shrinkage frameworks and their practical application especially for asset optimization, and then they also discussed on a new category of shrinkage-based techniques for the means of return and the corresponding covariance matrix, as well as, the weights in the asset. As a slight enhancement for this research approach, the work of Candelon et al. (2012) presented such a kind of double shrinkage adaptation to improve the general stability of the estimation on even small sample sizes covariance matrices via taking into account a ridge regression approach to shrink the all the weights towards the equally-weighted asset.

Clearly, the selection of covariance matrix estimators influences the performance of optimized portfolios. The above approaches for covariance matrix estimations pose an opportunity for investors, who usually apply the traditional estimator of sample covariance matrix, to improve their portfolio performance by altering the new estimators of covariance matrix in their portfolio optimization models. The problem is that there is not a complete and sure research base regarding the effectiveness of out – of – sample performance when making changes to covariance matrix estimations. In the other words, there is no solid foundation involved in this field, and portfolio managers would not risk their money to make investments based on unproven or rigorous research.

Moreover, the traditional estimator of covariance matrix is facing many difficulties and does not bring the expected results because the development of the financial market has resulted in the number of investment assets in the market increasing rapidly and much larger than the observed sample, from that requiring the new estimators of covariance matrix to be studied and applied. Besides, there is still a lot of controversy surrounding the applicability and effectiveness of covariance matrix estimation methods in different markets.

Furthermore, the robust estimators of covariance matrix are mainly applied and tested in the developed markets; there are not many researches on emerging and developing financial market. In particular, there is almost no research in Vietnam related to the selection of covariance matrix estimators for optimizing the portfolios, especially in the shrinkage methods. Therefore, there is a gap for the author to investigate the level of influence of covariance matrix estimators on the minimum – variances optimized portfolios, and to test the performance of these estimators on Vietnam stock market.

3. Research Methodology

In order to achieve the research objectives and answer the above questions, the author needs to choose an appropriate research method. In this dissertation, the author applied some research methodology as follows:

First, there are six estimators of covariance matrix used in this study to examine how the change of covariance matrix estimation affects the optimal portfolio selection. These estimators of covariance matrix includes the sample covariance matrix (SCM), the single index model (SIM), the constant correlation model (CCM), the shrinkage towards single index model (SSIM), the shrinkage towards constant correlation model (SCCM), and the shrinkage towards identity matrix (STIM). In which, SCM is seen as the traditional or standard estimator of covariance matrix while SIM and CCM are called as model – based approaches; and SSIM, SCCM, STIM are mentioned as shrinkage methods. In addition, the minimum – variance optimization is selected for generating the optimal portfolios through the estimated covariance matrices by the above estimators.

Second, to evaluate the feasibility and potential application of the estimators of covariance matrix mentioned above, a back-testing process based on the Python programming language has been developed and applied in this study. The back – testing process was simulated on the back – testing platform in the previous research of Tran et al. (2020). The statistical properties of estimators of covariance matrix will be examined and clarified by the back – testing procedure, from that providing insight into whether which estimator will be able to make profit in the reality.

Third, through the back – testing process, the portfolio performance metrics which are considered as the important criteria for evaluating the portfolios will be estimated. Besides of the basic portfolio evaluation criteria such as portfolio return and volatility of portfolio, other useful evaluation criteria are also calculated in this research including portfolio turnover, maximum drawdown, winning rate and Jensen’s Alpha. In order to calculate these portfolio evaluation criteria, the author used a “rolling – horizon” technique that defines as a reactive scheduling method that “solves iteratively the deterministic problem by moving forward the optimization horizon in every iteration; assuming that the status of the system is updated as soon as the different uncertain or not accurate enough parameters became to be known, the optimal schedule for the new resulting scenario (and optimization horizon) may be found” Silvente et al.(2015). The rolling – horizon approach allows the investors to update or adjust their input data for optimal portfolio selection based on currently available information. The technique will be presented more clearly in the next sections. Moreover, the input data for the back - testing process are weekly stock price series, which will then be converted to weekly return during the optimization procedure. One more thing, when calculating the portfolio performance metrics, the transaction costs are also considered at every rebalancing point.

Lastly, these estimated performance metrics are applied for comparing the differences among the estimators of covariance matrix in selecting the optimal portfolios. To make sure that there are significant differences of performance metrics between the two certain estimators, the p – values are computed following the bootstrapping methodology that is mentioned in the research of DeMiguel (2009).

4. Results

During this period, many foreign fund management companies also joined Vietnam's stock market. Investment results show that investment funds in the period of 2009 - 2019 have relatively good investment results compared to the average growth rate of Vietnam's stock market (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1: The performance of investment funds in the period of 2009 - 2019

According to research by Brinson, Singer, Beebover (1991), asset allocation activity has a 91.5% impact on the investment results of the portfolio, while securities selection, buying, and selling time and other factors affecting only about 9% of the portfolio results.

First, the application of quantitative methods in asset allocation and optimal portfolio selection is quite new in Vietnam's stock market, especially for individual investors. The majority of investors in the Vietnamese stock market are individual investors, who mostly use fundamental and technical analysis methods to select stocks. The optimal investment portfolio construction is primarily selected by investors according to their own feelings or subjective judgments, not based on specific quantitative methods. Besides, there are also a few individual investors actively in using quantitative models to choose optimal portfolios. However, these models are traditional models with certain limitations and not highly applicable.

Next, the particularities of the Vietnam stock market make it difficult for investors, especially for investment funds who want to apply quantitative models in choosing optimal portfolios. The first is data problem. Although the Vietnamese stock market has gone through 20 years of development; however in the early stages, the number of companies participating in the market is not much, and the quality of information stored in this period is also not guaranteed. This affects not only the length of the data but also its quality. Meanwhile, we know that today's modern methods of portfolio optimization require the size of research data to be large enough and the reliability of the data to be guaranteed. Moreover, regulations on the Vietnamese stock market make it difficult for investors to build optimal portfolios using quantitative models. For example, the regulations of daily trading limit on HOSE ($\pm 7\%$) and HNX ($\pm 10\%$), UPCoM ($\pm 15\%$). This means that the prices of stocks on the market can only fluctuate by a certain margin regardless of how bad or good the market moves. The regulation can help stabilize investors' sentiment during periods of deep decline or hot bull market, but it also prevents the market events from being fully reflected in the prices of stocks, making it difficult for investors to forecast the fluctuation of their portfolio in the future.

Furthermore, the delay settlement date of a stock is up to some business days that influence the testing and adoption of portfolio optimization models. Investors who execute a buying transaction of stock today (), they must be waiting for three business days (T+3) to be able to selling this stock on Vietnam stock market. Besides, after they sell this stock, they need to wait two more business days (T+2) to start with another buying transaction or accept interest payments to the stock company during these two days to have money to support their buying transaction immediately. These limitations of Vietnam stock market increase risks and incur much transaction costs for investors. Moreover, these restrictions also make it difficult to apply the high – frequency trading models on the Vietnamese stock market. Therefore, in the process of building the optimal portfolio

selection models, they need to consider and calculate the impact of these restrictions on their models when applying the models in practice.

Moreover, the liquidity risk is also one of the important factors leading to deviations in the practical application of portfolio optimization models. The market size is small and the number of shares traded during the day is not much, leading to high liquidity risks for investors when they want to buy or sell stocks in large quantities. Thus, when developing and back-testing the quantitative models, investors need to pay attention to this slippage factor in the stock trading activity, especially the transactions with large volume of buying and selling in their portfolios. Otherwise, the theoretical buying and selling prices could be significantly different from the actual buying and selling prices, which in turn affects the reliability of the optimal portfolio selection models.

Therefore, the research and selection of an appropriate portfolio optimization method is essential for investors on the Vietnam stock market. In the next sections, the author will focus on presenting suitable methods in selecting the optimal investment portfolios on the stock market in general and the Vietnamese stock market in particular.

5. Conclusion

Optimizing the securities portfolio is always an interesting problem for investors in the market. These investors attempt to build a portfolio that meets their expected return and has limited risk. They only accept a higher level of risk when compensated by a reasonable expected return. If two portfolios have the same expected return, the portfolio with lower risk would be selected. Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT) that was firstly introduced by Harry Markowitz in 1952 is usually applied to address above issue. Although this theory has been applied widely, this theory still has some limitations, leading to unexpected results in real life. These limitations mainly come from the instability of expected return and estimated covariance matrix, which are the significant parameters in MPT for portfolio selection. This leads the portfolio from MPT model to fluctuate continuously over time and to suffer high transaction costs when applying in practice.

Moreover, with the rapid development of the current financial market, the application of this theory has become more and more difficult because the number of stocks in the market quickly increased and even exceeded the number of observed samples. The superiority between the number of stocks compared to the amount of observed samples makes it difficult for traditional methods to choose the optimal portfolio, since there is not enough information required to make a decision. From there, we can see that the research and development of portfolio selection models is an urgent issue for investors, portfolio managers and researchers.

REFERENCES

- i. Bai, J., and Shi, S. (2011). *Estimating high dimensional covariance matrices and its applications. Annals of Economics and Finance*, 12: 199–215.
- ii. Broadie, M. (1993). *Computing efficient frontiers using estimated parameters. Annals of operations research*, 45:21-58.
- iii. Best, J., and Grauer, R. (1991). *Sensitivity analysis for mean-variance portfolio problems. Management Science*, 37(8):980–989.
- iv. Bengtsson, C., and Holst, J. (2002). *On portfolio selection: Improved covariance matrix estimation for Swedish asset returns. Journal of Portfolio Management*, 33(4): 55-63.
- v. Chan, L., Jason, K., and Josef, L. (1999). *On portfolio optimization: Forecasting covariances and choosing the risk model. The Review of Financial Studies*, 12(5):937–974.
- vi. Chandra, S. (2003). *Regional Economy Size and the Growth-Instability Frontier: Evidence from Europe. J. Reg. Sci.*, 43(1): 95-122. doi:10.1111/1467-9787.00291.
- vii. Chekhlov, A., and Uryasev, S. (2005). *Drawdown measure in portfolio optimization. International Journal of Theoretical and Applied Finance*, 8(1):13-58.
- viii. Chen, Y., Ami W., Yonina E., and Alfred, H. (2010). *Shrinkage algorithms for MMSE covariance estimation. IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, 58: 5016–29.

- ix. Chopra, V., and Ziemba, W.(1993). *The effect of errors in means, variances, and covariances on optimal portfolio choice. Journal of Portfolio Management*, 19(2):6- 11.
- x. Clarke, Roger G., Harindra De Silva, and Steven Thorley. (2006). *Minimum-variance portfolios in the U.S. equity market. Journal of Portfolio Management*, 33: 10–24.
- xi. Cohen, J., and Pogue, J. (1967). *An empirical evaluation of alternative portfolio selection models. The Journal of Business*, 40(2):166–193.
- xii. De Nard, G., Ledoit, O., and Wolf, M. (2019). *Factor models for portfolio selection in large dimensions: The good, the better and the ugly. Journal of Financial Econometrics. Forthcoming.*
- xiii. DeMiguel, V., and Francisco N., (2009). *Portfolio selection with robust estimation. Operations Research*, 57(3):560–577.
- xiv. Efron, B., R. Tibshirani. (1993). *An Introduction to the Bootstrap. Chapman and Hall, New York.*
- xv. Edwin, J., Martin, G., and Manfred, P. (1997). *Simple rules for optimal portfolio selection: the multi group case. Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 12(3):329–345.
- xvi. Elton, Edwin J., and Martin J Gruber. (1973). *Estimating the dependence structure of share prices: implications for portfolio selection. The Journal of Finance*, 28(5):1203– 1232.
- xvii. Elton, Edwin J., Martin J Gruber., Stephen B., and William N Goetzmann.(2009). *Modern portfolio theory and investment analysis. John Wiley & Sons.*
- xviii. Ernest, Chan P. (2009). *Quantitative trading: How to Build Your Own Algorithmic Trading Business. John Wiley & Sons.*
- xix. Ernest, Chan P. (2013). *Algorithmic Trading: Winning Strategies and Their Rationale. John Wiley & Sons.*
- xx. Fabozzi, F., Gupta, F., and Markowitz, H.(2002). *The legacy of modern portfolio theory. The Journal of Investing*, 11(3): 7–22.
- xxi. Fama, E., and French, K. (1993). *Common risk factors in the returns on stocks and bonds. The Journal of Financial Economics*, 33: 3–56.
- xxii. Fama, E., and French, K. (2015). *A five-factor asset pricing model. Journal of Financial Economics*, 16: 1–22.
- xxiii. Fama, E., and French, K. (2016). *Dissecting Anomalies with a Five-Factor Model. Review of Financial Studies*, 29: 69–103.
- xxiv. Fernández, A., and Gómez, S. (2007). *Portfolio selection using neural networks. Computers and Operations Research*, 34: 1177–91.
- xxv. Frankfurter, G., Phillips, H., and Seagle, J. (1971). *Portfolio Selection: The Effects of Uncertain Means, Variances, and Covariances. Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 6(5):1251 – 1262.
- xxvi. George Derpanopoulos (2018). *Optimal financial portfolio selection. Working paper.*
- xxvii. Haugen, Robert A., and Nardin L. Baker. (1991). *The efficient market inefficiency of capitalization-weighted stock portfolios. Journal of Portfolio Management*, 17: 35– 40.
- xxviii. Huber, P. J. (2004). *Robust Statistics. John Wiley & Sons, New York.*
- xxix. Ikeda, Y., and Kubokawa, T. (2016). *Linear shrinkage estimation of large covariance matrices using factor models. Journal of Multivariate Analysis*, 152: 61–81.
- xxx. Iyiola, O., Munirat, Y., and Christopher, N.(2012). *The modern portfolio theory as an investment decision tool. Journal of Accounting and Taxation*, 4(2):19-28.
- xxxi. Jagannathan, R., and Ma, T., (2003). *Risk reduction in large portfolios: Why imposing the wrong constraints helps. The Journal of Finance*, 58(4):1651–1683.
- xxxii. James, W. and Stein, C. (1961). *Estimation with quadratic loss. In Proceedings of the Fourth Berkeley Symposium on Mathematical Statistics and Probability 1, pages 361– 380.*
- xxxiii. Jensen, M.(1968). *The performance of mutual funds in the period 1945 – 1964. Journal of Finance*, 23(2):389-416.
- xxxiv. Jobson, J., Korkie, B. (1980). *Estimation for Markowitz efficient portfolios. Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 75(371): 544 – 554.

- xxxv. Jorion, P. (1985). *International Portfolio Diversification with Estimation Risk*. *Journal of Business*, 58: 259–78.
- xxxvi. Jorion, P. (1986). *Bayes-Stein estimation for portfolio analysis*. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 21(3):279–292.
- xxxvii. Kwan, Clarence C.Y. (2011). *An introduction to shrinkage estimation of the covariance matrix: A Pedagogic Illustration*. *Spreadsheets in Education (eJSiE)*, 4(3): article 6.
- xxxviii. Kempf, A., and Memmel, C. (2006). *Estimating the global minimum variance portfolio*. *Schmalenbach Business Review*, 58:332-48.
- xxxix. Konno, Y. (2009). *Shrinkage estimators for large covariance matrices in multivariate real and complex normal distributions under an invariant quadratic loss*. *Journal of Multivariate Analysis*, 100: 2237–53.
- xl. Lam, C. (2016). *Nonparametric eigenvalue-regularized precision or covariance matrix estimator*. *Annals of Statistics*, 44(3):928–953.
- xli. Liagkouras, K., and Kostas M. (2018). *Multi-period mean-variance fuzzy portfolio optimization model with transaction costs*. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 67: 260–69.
- xlii. Ledoit, O. and Peche, S. (2011). *Eigenvectors of some large sample covariance matrix ensembles*. *Probability Theory and Related Fields*, 150(1–2):233–264.
- xliii. Ledoit, O. and Wolf, M. (2003a). *Honey, I shrunk the sample covariance matrix*. *Journal of Portfolio Management*, 30(4):110–119.
- xliv. Ledoit, O. and Wolf, M. (2003b). *Improved estimation of the covariance matrix of stock returns with an application to portfolio selection*. *Journal of Empirical Finance*, 10(5):603–621.
- xlv. Ledoit, O. and Wolf, M. (2004). *A well-conditioned estimator for large-dimensional covariance matrices*. *Journal of Multivariate Analysis*, 88(2):365–411.
- xlvi. Ledoit, O. and Wolf, M. (2008). *Robust performance hypothesis testing with the Sharpe ratio*. *Journal of Empirical Finance*, 15(5):850–859.
- xlvii. Ledoit, O. and Wolf, M. (2012). *Nonlinear shrinkage estimation of large-dimensional covariance matrices*. *Annals of Statistics*, 40(2):1024–1060.
- xlviii. Ledoit, O. and Wolf, M. (2015). *Spectrum estimation: A unified framework for covariance matrix estimation and PCA in large dimensions*. *Journal of Multivariate Analysis*, 139(2):360–384.
- xlix. Ledoit, O. and Wolf, M. (2017a). *Nonlinear shrinkage of the covariance matrix for portfolio selection: Markowitz meets Goldilocks*. *Review of Financial Studies*, 30(12):4349–4388.
- l. Ledoit, O. and Wolf, M. (2017b). *Numerical implementation of the QuEST function*. *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis*, 115:199–223.
- li. Ledoit, O. and Wolf, M. (2018b). *Optimal estimation of a large-dimensional covariance matrix under Stein's loss*. *Bernoulli*, 24(4B). 3791–3832.
- liii. Markowitz, H. (1952). *Portfolio selection*. *Journal of Finance*, 7:77–91.
- liv. Martin, D., Clark, A., and Christopher G. (2010). *Robust portfolio construction*. *Handbook of Portfolio Construction*. Springer, 337–380.
- lv. Merton, R. (1969). *Life time portfolio selection under uncertainty: The continuous-time case*. *The review of Economics and Statistics*, 51: 247–57.
- lvi. Merton, R. (1971). *Optimum consumption and portfolio rules in a continuous-time model*. *Journal of Economic Theory*, 3: 373–413.
- lvii. Merton, R. (1972). *An analytic derivation of the efficient portfolio frontier*. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 7: 1851–72.
- lviii. Merton, C. (1980). *On estimating the expected return on the market: An exploratory investigation*. *Journal of financial economics*, 8(4):323–361.
- lix. Michaud, Richard O. (1989). *The Markowitz optimization enigma: Is "optimized" optimal*. *Financial Analysts Journal*, 45(1):31–42.
- lx. Michaud, Richard O., Esch, D., and Michaud, R. (2012). *Deconstructing Black- Litterman: How to get the Portfolio you already knew you wanted*. Available at SSRN 2641893.

- lxi. Nick Radge (2006). *Adaptive analysis for Australian stocks*. Wrightbooks.
- lxii. Nguyen, Tho. (2010). *Arbitrage Pricing Theory: Evidence from an Emerging Stock Market*, Working Papers 03, Development and Policies Research Center (DEPOCEN), Vietnam.
- lxiii. Okhrin, Yarema, and Wolfgang Schmid. (2007). *Comparison of different estimation techniques for portfolio selection*. *Asta Advances in Statistical Analysis*, 91: 109–27.
- lxiv. Pogue, A. (1970). *An extension of the Markowitz portfolio selection model to include variable transactions' costs, short sales, leverage policies and taxes*. *The Journal of Finance*, 25: 1005–27.
- lxv. Ross, S. A. (1976). *The arbitrage theory of capital asset pricing*. *Journal of Economic Theory*, 13(3):341–360.
- lxvi. Samuelson, A. (1969). *Life time portfolio selection by dynamic stochastic programming*. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 51: 239–46.
- lxvii. Schöfer, J. and Strimmer, K. (2005). *A shrinkage approach to large-scale covariance matrix estimation and implications for functional genomics*. *Statistical Applications in Genetics and Molecular Biology*, 4(1). Article 32.
- lxviii. Soleimani, H., Golmakani, H., and Mohammad S. (2009). *Markowitz-based portfolio selection with minimum transaction lots, cardinality constraints and regarding sector capitalization using genetic algorithm*. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 36: 5058–63.
- lxix. Sharpe, William F. (1963). *A simplified model for portfolio analysis*. *Management science*, 9(2):277–293.
- lxx. Sharpe, William F. (1964). *Capital asset prices: A theory of market equilibrium under conditions of risk*. *The journal of finance*, 19(3):425–442.
- lxxi. Stein, C. (1956). *Inadmissibility of the usual estimator for the mean of a multivariate normal distribution*. In *Proceedings of the Third Berkeley Symposium on Mathematical Statistics and Probability*, pages 197–206. University of California Press.
- lxxii. Stein, C. (1986). *Lectures on the theory of estimation of many parameters*. *Journal of Mathematical Sciences*, 34(1):1373–1403.
- lxxiii. Taleb, N. (2007). *The Black Swan: The Impact of the Highly Improbable*, Random House, 80-120.
- lxxiv. Truong, L., and Duong, T. (2014). *Fama and French three-factor model: Empirical evidences from the Ho Chi Minh Stock Exchange*. *Journal of Science Can Tho University*, 32:61 – 68.
- lxxv. Vo, Q., and Nguyen, H. (2011). *Measuring risk tolerance and establishing an optimal portfolio for individual investors in HOSE*. *Economic Development Review*, 33-38.
- lxxvi. Xue, Hong-Gang, Cheng-Xian Xu, and Zong-Xian Feng. (2006). *Mean-variance portfolio optimal problem under concave transaction cost*. *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, 174: 1–12.
- lxxvii. Yang, L., Romain, C., and Matthew, M. (2014). *Minimum variance portfolio optimization with robust shrinkage covariance estimation*. Paper presented at 2014 48th Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems and Computers, Pacific Grove, CA, USA, November 2–5; pp. 1326–30.